

README for data and code for "Thermal limits of survival and reproduction depend on stress duration: a case study of *Drosophila suzukii*". <https://zenodo.org/records/10602268>

Contains three scripts with accompanying data for reproducing analyses and figures in the manuscript:

1. `doseresponse_alltraits_bothsexes.R`: fits and plots dose-response curves using the 'drc' package for mortality, coma, and productivity for temperatures 34-38 °C. Uses data in "alltraits_summary_R3.csv" to fit dose-response curves (Fig. 1) and calculate Lt_{50} for mortality or Et_{50} for coma and productivity
2. `coma_proxy_alltraits.R`: this script determines the validity of thermal coma as proxies for mortality and productivity. Uses data in "all_data_long_R3.csv" to calculate proportions dead/alive and average productivity among early vs. late onset coma groups (Fig. 3)
3. `microclimate_injury_accumulation.R` - uses data in "TDT_parameters_R3.csv" (derived from Fig. 2 with data shown in Supporting Table 2) and modelled microclimate to estimate accumulated heat injury (per minute) for all traits across the year 2018. On a representative summer day (Aug 5), injury accumulation during the day is shown in Fig. 4.

For any inquiries or bugs, please contact corresponding author Michael Ørsted (moer@bio.aau.dk)

METADATA

Metadata for the above data files are supplied below

File	Column_header	Description
all_data_long_R3.csv	id	unique ID
	temp	Exposure temperature [°C]
	lvl	Exposure duration in % of estimated median t_{coma} based on initial TDT curves
	time	Exposure duration in minutes
	sex	M/F for males/females
	rep	replicate vial
	prod	offspring / female / day
	sterile	0: producing offspring, 1: not producing offspring
	dead	0: alive, 1: dead
	t_coma	t_{coma} [mins]
alltraits_summary_R3.csv	treatment_sex_id	temperature_lvl_sex ID
	temp	Exposure temperature [°C]
	lvl	Exposure duration in % of estimated median t_{coma} based on initial TDT curves
	time	Exposure duration in minutes
	sex	M/F for males/females
	surv	proportion alive
	prod	Average offspring / female / day
	fertile	Proportion w. offspring
	awake	Proportion NOT in a coma

TDT_parameters_R3.csv	trait	coma, mortality (mort), productivity (fecund)
	sex	M/F for males/females
	intercept	intercept of linear regression of log10(time) [min] regressed on temperature [°C]
	z	the thermal sensitivity coefficient determined as - 1/slope of the linear regression of log10(time) [min] regressed on temperature [°C]
	R2	Coefficient of determination
	p	significance of linear regression of log10(time) [min] regressed on temperature [°C]
	Q10	Thermal quotient. Rate change resulting from a 10 °C temperature change. Calculated as $10^{(10/z)}$
	sCTmax1h	Temperature resulting in thermal failure for each trait after 1 h. Interpolated from the linear regression of log10(time) [min] regressed on temperature [°C]
	sCTmax4h	Temperature resulting in thermal failure for each trait after 4 h. Interpolated from the linear regression of log10(time) [min] regressed on temperature [°C]